

EXISTENCE AND STABILITY OF NON-COLLINEAR LIBRATION POINTS IN RESTRICTED THREE-BODY PROBLEM WHEN SMALLER PRIMARY IS A PROLATE SPHEROID

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Abstract

In this paper the existence and stability of non-collinear libration points in the restricted three-body problem has been discussed when the smaller primary is a prolate spheroid. We have determined the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass and then we have investigated the non-collinear libration points and their stability in linear sense. This is found that there exist two non-collinear libration points are stable for a critical value of mass parameter $\mu = \mu_c \leq 0.0559836$.

Key Words: Celestial Mechanics, Restricted three-body problem, Prolate Spheroid, Libration points, Linear Stability.

Introduction

The restricted problem of three bodies is a well known problem and studied by many mathematicians, physicists and astronomers. Khanna and Bhatnagar (1999) have discussed the stationary solutions of the planar restricted three body problem when the smaller primary is a triaxial rigid body with one of the axes as the axis of symmetry and its equatorial plane coinciding with the plane of motion. The bigger primary is taken as an oblate spheroid and its equatorial plane is also coinciding with the plane of motion. They have shown that there exist five libration points, two triangular and three collinear. The collinear points are unstable, while the triangular points are stable for the mass parameter $0 \leq \mu < \mu_{\text{crit}}$ (the critical mass parameter) and the triangular points have long or short periodic elliptical orbits in the same range of μ .

Sosnytskyi (2005) has studied the relationship between the Hill stability of a fixed pair of mass points and the Lagrange stability of a system of three mass points and established some relations that connect separately the squared mutual distances between mass points and the squared distances between mass points and the barycenter of the system.

Raheem and Singh (2006) have investigated the stability of equilibrium points under the influence of small perturbations in the coriolis and centrifugal forces, together with the effects of oblateness and radiation pressures of the primaries. They have found that the collinear points remain unstable while the triangular points are stable for $0 \leq \mu < \mu_c$ and unstable for $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$, where μ_c is the critical mass parameter depends upon the coriolis force, centrifugal force, oblateness and radiation pressure of the primaries.

Narayan and Kumar (2011) have studied the effects of the oblateness and the photogravitational of the bigger primary and the oblateness of the smaller primary on the location of the triangular Lagrangian equilibrium points in the elliptical restricted three-body problem. They observed that the range of stability decreases as the oblateness and the radiation pressure parameter increases.

Tkhai (2012) discussed the stability of the collinear libration points in the photogravitational three body problem and shown that these points are stable in a Lyapunov sense in the case of a fourth-order resonance.

Abouelmagd and Sharaf (2012) have discussed the existence of libration points and their linear stability when the more massive primary is radiating and the smaller is an oblate spheroid. They observed that the collinear points remain unstable while the triangular points are stable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \mu_c$, and unstable in the range $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq 1/2$, where $0 < \mu_c < 1/2$. They also found the relations for periodic orbits around five libration points with their semimajor, semiminor axes, eccentricities, the frequencies of orbits and periods.

Idrisi and Taqvi (2013) have studied a problem in the restricted three body problem in which the smaller primary is an ellipsoid and the bigger is point mass. This paper deals with the existence and the stability of the libration points in the restricted three-body problem when the smaller primary is an ellipsoid. They have determined the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass which involves elliptic integrals and then investigated the collinear and non collinear libration points and their stability. They have also proved in their work that there exist five collinear libration points L_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) and the non-collinear libration points lie on the arc of the unit circle centered at the bigger primary and both the collinear and non-collinear libration points are unstable for $0 < \mu \leq 1/2$ and $0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2$.

Singh et. al. (2013) have investigated the motion of an infinitesimal body in the generalized restricted three-body problem. It is generalized in the sense that both primaries are radiating, oblate bodies, together with the effect of gravitational potential from a belt. They have been found that, in addition to the usual five equilibrium points, there appear two new collinear points L_{n1} , L_{n2} due to the potential from the belt, and in the presence of all these perturbations, the equilibrium points L_1 , L_3 come nearer to the primaries; while L_2 , L_4 , L_5 , L_{n1} move towards the less massive primary and L_{n2} moves away from it. The collinear equilibrium points remain unstable, while the triangular points are stable for $0 < \mu < \mu_c$ and unstable for $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq 1/2$.

Abouelmagd et. al. (2013) have studied the generalized restricted three-body problem, generalized in the sense that the effects of oblateness of the three participating bodies as well as the small perturbations in the Coriolis and centrifugal forces are considered. They have shown the existence of equilibrium points, their linear stability and the periodic orbits around these points under these effects. They have found that the positions of the collinear points and y -coordinate of the triangular points are not affected by the small perturbations in the Coriolis force while x -coordinate of the triangular points is neither affected by the small perturbations in the Coriolis force nor the oblateness of the third body. Furthermore, the critical mass value and the elements of periodic orbits around the equilibrium points such as the semi-major and the

semi-minor axes, the angular frequencies and corresponding periods may change by all the parameters of oblateness as well as the small perturbations in the Coriolis and centrifugal forces.

Reena Kumari et. al. (2014) have extended the basic model of the restricted four-body problem introducing two bigger dominant primaries m_1 and m_2 as oblate spheroids when masses of the two primary bodies (m_2 and m_3) are equal. The aim of this study is to investigate the use of zero velocity surfaces and the Poincaré surfaces of section to determine the possible allowed boundary regions and the stability orbit of the equilibrium points. According to different values of Jacobi constant C , we can determine boundary region where the particle can move in possible permitted zones. The stability regions of the equilibrium points expanded due to presence of oblateness coefficient and various values of C , whereas for certain range of t ($100 \leq t \leq 200$), orbits form a shape of cote's spiral. For different values of oblateness parameters A_1 ($0 < A_1 < 1$) and A_2 ($0 < A_2 < 1$), they obtained two collinear and six non-collinear equilibrium points. The non-collinear equilibrium points are stable when the mass parameter μ lies in the interval (0.0190637, 0.647603). However, basins of attraction are constructed with the help of Newton Raphson method to demonstrate the convergence as well as divergence region of the equilibrium points. The nature of basins of attraction of the equilibrium points are less affected in presence and absence of oblateness coefficients A_1 and A_2 respectively in the proposed model.

Singh et. al. (2014) have investigated the motion of a test particle in the vicinity of a binary made of a triaxial primary and a spherical companion moving along elliptic orbits about their common barycenter in the neighborhood of collinear libration points. Their positions and stability are found to be affected by the triaxiality of the bigger primary, and by the semi-major axis and the eccentricity of the binary's orbits as well. The analytic results obtained are applied to binary neutron stars consisting of a bigger triaxial primary and a spherical companion. A numerical analysis shows that the positions of the collinear points of PSR J1518+4904, PSR B1534+12, PSR B1914+16, and PSR B2127+11c are affected by the triaxiality of the bigger primary, and by the eccentricity of the orbits. The stability behavior however remains unchanged: the collinear points remain unstable in the Lyapunov sense.

Idrisi and Taqvi (2014) have investigated the location and stability of the non-collinear libration points when both the primaries are ellipsoids and found that the non-collinear libration points exist only in the interval $52^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$ and form an isosceles triangle with the primaries. Further they observed that the non collinear libration points are unstable in $52^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$.

Idrisi (2014) has discussed the existence and stability of the libration points in the restricted three-body problem when the smaller primary is an oblate spheroid. He has determined the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass and then investigated the collinear and non-collinear libration points and their stability in linear sense. He has found that there exist three collinear libration points and the non-collinear libration points are lying on the circumference of the unit circle whose center is the bigger primary. Further he observed that the collinear and non-collinear libration points all are unstable.

2. Potential of a solid homogeneous prolate spheroid at an external point

Let a, b, c be the semi-axes of the given prolate spheroid such that $a = b < c$ and x, y, z the coordinates of the external point P . Let a', b', c' be the semi-axes of the confocal prolate spheroid which passes through P .

Let the equation of the prolate spheroid be

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1, \quad (1)$$

The equation of the confocal prolate spheroid whose semi-axes are a', b' and c' such that $a' = b' < c'$ which passes through the point $P(x, y, z)$ is

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a'^2} + \frac{z^2}{c'^2} = 1 \quad (2)$$

Since the prolate spheroids are confocal, we have $a'^2 = a^2 + \kappa$, $b'^2 = b^2 + \kappa$ and $c'^2 = c^2 + \kappa$.

Therefore, the Equation (2) becomes (MacMillan, 1958),

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2 + \kappa} + \frac{z^2}{c^2 + \kappa} = 1 \quad (3)$$

The Equation (3) is a second degree equation in κ . On solving the Equation (3), we get

$$\kappa_1 = 0 \text{ and } \kappa_2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - a^2 - c^2.$$

Obviously the largest root of the Equation (3) is κ_2 , we supposed that $\kappa_2 = \kappa$, therefore

$$\kappa = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - a^2 - c^2 = r^2 - a^2 - c^2. \quad (4)$$

where r is the distance between the center of mass of prolate spheroid and $P(x, y, z)$.

The potential of the prolate spheroid with axes a and c and density σ at an external point $P(x, y, z)$ is given by (MacMillan, 1958),

$$V = \frac{2\pi\sigma a^2 c}{\sqrt{c^2 - a^2}} \left(1 + \frac{x^2 + y^2 - 2z^2}{2(c^2 - a^2)} \right) \sinh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{c^2 - a^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} - \frac{\pi\sigma a^2 c \sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{c^2 - a^2} \frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2 + \kappa} + \frac{\pi\sigma a^2 c}{c^2 - a^2} \frac{2z^2}{\sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}, \quad (5)$$

where κ is defined in the equation (4).

3. Equations of motion

Let m_2 be a prolate spheroid whose axes are a , b and c ($a = b < c$) and m_1 a point mass ($m_1 > m_2$), are moving in the circular orbits around their center of mass O . An infinitesimal mass m_3 is moving in the plane of motion of m_1 and m_2 . The distances of m_3 from m_1 , m_2 and O are r_1 , r_2 and r respectively (Fig. 1). The principal axes of spheroid remains parallel to the synodic axes $Oxyz$ throughout the motion and the equatorial plane of m_2 is coincide with the plane of motion of m_1 and m_2 . Let the line joining m_1 and m_2 be taken as X -axis and O their center of mass as origin. Let the line passing through O and perpendicular to OX and lying in the plane of motion m_1 and m_2 be the Y -axis. Let us consider a synodic system of co-ordinates $Oxyz$ initially coincide with the inertial system $OXYZ$, rotating with angular velocity ω about Z -axis (the z -axis is coincide with Z -axis). We wish to find the equations of motion of m_3 using the terminology of Szebehely (1967) in the synodic co-ordinate system and dimensionless variables *i.e.* the distance between the primaries is unity, the unit of time t is such that the gravitational constant $G = 1$ and the sum of the masses of the primaries is unity *i.e.* $m_1 + m_2 = 1$.

Fig. 1: The Configuration of the R3BP when m_2 is a prolate spheroid

The potential of the prolate spheroid m_2 at $P(x, y)$ in our case is therefore given by,

$$V = \frac{3m_2}{4(c^2 - a^2)} \left[\frac{2(c^2 - a^2) + r_2^2}{\sqrt{c^2 - a^2}} \sinh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{c^2 - a^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} - \frac{r_2^2 \sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{a^2 + \kappa} \right], \quad (6)$$

where

$$m_2 = \frac{4}{3} \pi a^2 c \sigma = \text{Mass of the prolate spheroid,}$$

$$\kappa = r_2^2 - a^2 - c^2,$$

$$r_2 = \sqrt{(x - x_2)^2 + y^2}.$$

The equations of the motion of m_3 in the synodic co-ordinate system and dimensionless variables are:

$$m_3 [\partial^2 \mathbf{r} / \partial t^2 + 2 \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \partial \mathbf{r} / \partial t + \partial \boldsymbol{\omega} / \partial t \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{r})] = \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mathbf{r} = x \mathbf{i} + y \mathbf{j},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = n \mathbf{k},$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \text{Total force acting on } m_3 = \mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2,$$

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = \text{Gravitational force exerted on } m_3 \text{ due to } m_1,$$

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = \text{Gravitational force exerted on } m_3 \text{ due to } m_2.$$

We first calculate the L.H.S. of the Equation (7) in the Cartesian form as follows:

$$\partial \mathbf{r} / \partial t = \dot{x} \mathbf{i} + \dot{y} \mathbf{j},$$

$$\text{Relative acceleration} = \partial^2 \mathbf{r} / \partial t^2 = \ddot{x} \mathbf{i} + \ddot{y} \mathbf{j},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{r} = -n y \mathbf{i} + n x \mathbf{j},$$

$$\text{Coriolis acceleration} = \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \partial \mathbf{r} / \partial t = -n \dot{y} \mathbf{i} + n \dot{x} \mathbf{j},$$

$$\text{Centrifugal acceleration} = \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{r}) = -n^2(x \mathbf{i} + y \mathbf{j}),$$

$$\partial \boldsymbol{\omega} / \partial t = 0,$$

$$\text{Euler's acceleration} = \partial \boldsymbol{\omega} / \partial t \times \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}.$$

Thus, the L.H.S. of the Equation (7) becomes

$$m_3 [(\ddot{x} \mathbf{i} + \ddot{y} \mathbf{j}) - 2n(\dot{y} \mathbf{i} - \dot{x} \mathbf{j}) - n^2(x \mathbf{i} + y \mathbf{j})]$$

Now, we calculate the R.H.S. of the Equation (7) as follows:

Let the gravitational potential of m_1 and m_2 at m_3 be V_1 and V_2 respectively, therefore

$$V_1 = \frac{-G m_1 m_3}{r_1},$$

$$V_2 = \frac{-3G m_2 m_3}{4(c^2 - a^2)} \left[\frac{2(c^2 - a^2) + r_2^2}{\sqrt{c^2 - a^2}} \sinh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{c^2 - a^2}{a^2 + \kappa}} - \frac{r_2^2 \sqrt{c^2 + \kappa}}{a^2 + \kappa} \right],$$

where

a, c = semi axes of the prolate spheroid m_2 ,

$$\kappa = r_2^2 - a^2 - c^2,$$

$$r_1^2 = (x - x_1)^2 + y^2,$$

$$r_2^2 = (x - x_2)^2 + y^2.$$

Let $c^2 - a^2 = A$, $A \ll 1$, therefore the potential of prolate spheroid in terms of oblateness factor A is given by

$$V_2 = -G m_2 m_3 \left[\frac{1}{r_2} - \frac{A}{10r_2^3} \right] \quad (8)$$

If $A = 0$, $V_2 = \frac{-G m_2 m_3}{r_2}$.

Now, Gravitational force exerted on m_3 due to m_1 and m_2 is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = -(\partial V_1 / \partial x \mathbf{i} + \partial V_1 / \partial y \mathbf{j}),$$

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = -(\partial V_2 / \partial x \mathbf{i} + \partial V_2 / \partial y \mathbf{j}).$$

Thus, the Equation (7) becomes

$$m_3[(\ddot{x}\mathbf{i} + \ddot{y}\mathbf{j}) - 2n(\dot{y}\mathbf{i} - \dot{x}\mathbf{j}) - n^2(x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j})] = -(\partial V_1 / \partial x + \partial V_2 / \partial x) \mathbf{i} - (\partial V_1 / \partial y + \partial V_2 / \partial y) \mathbf{j}$$

i. e.

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = n^2x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3}(x-\mu) - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3}(x+1-\mu) \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right), \quad (9)$$

and

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = n^2 y - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} y - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} y \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right). \quad (10)$$

where n is the mean-motion of the primaries,

$$\mu = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2},$$

$$1 - \mu = \frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2},$$

$$A = c^2 - a^2,$$

$$r_1^2 = (x - \mu)^2 + y^2,$$

$$r_2^2 = (x + 1 - \mu)^2 + y^2.$$

Now, we define a function Ω such that

$$\Omega = \frac{n^2}{2}(x^2 + y^2) + \frac{1-\mu}{r_1} + \frac{\mu}{r_2} \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right). \quad (11)$$

Hence, the Equations (9) and (10) become

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = \Omega_x, \quad (12)$$

$$\ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} = \Omega_y, \quad (13)$$

where Ω_x and Ω_y are the partial derivatives of Ω with respect to x and y respectively.

The integral analogous to Jacobi integral is

$$(\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2) = 2\Omega - C. \quad (14)$$

4. Calculation of the mean-motion n of the primaries

Since the primaries m_1 and m_2 are moving in the circular orbits around their center of mass O .

Therefore, the mean-motion n of the primaries is given by,

$$n^2 = \frac{F}{m_1 m_2}$$

where F is the gravitational force acting on m_1 due to m_2 .

Thus, the mean-motion n of the primaries is

$$n^2 = 1 - \frac{3A}{10}. \quad (15)$$

From the Equation (15), if $A = 0$, $n = 1$, which is the classical case of restricted three-body problem.

5. Libration Points

The libration points are the singularities of the manifold

$$F(x, y, \dot{x}, \dot{y}) \equiv \dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2 - 2\Omega + C = 0$$

and these points are given by the Equations

$$F_{\dot{x}} = F_{\dot{y}} = F_x = F_y = 0$$

$$i.e. \dot{x} = 0, \dot{y} = 0, \Omega_x = 0, \Omega_y = 0.$$

Therefore,

$$\Omega_x \equiv n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} (x+1-\mu) \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) = 0, \quad (16)$$

$$\Omega_y \equiv y \left[n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) \right] = 0. \quad (17)$$

5.1 Non-collinear Libration Points

The non-collinear libration points are the solution of the equations $\Omega_x = 0$ and $\Omega_y = 0$, $y \neq 0$ i.e.

$$n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} (x+1-\mu) \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) = 0, \quad (18)$$

$$n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) = 0. \quad (19)$$

On eliminating r_1 from the Equations (18) and (19), we have

$$n^2 - \frac{1}{r_2^3} \left(1 - \frac{3A}{10r_2^2} \right) = 0 \quad (20)$$

Obviously $r_2 = 1$ is the solution of the Equation (20).

Again eliminating r_2 from the Equations (18) and (19), we then get $r_1 = 1 + \frac{A}{30}$.

On solving the Equations $r_1 = 1 + \frac{A}{30}$ and $r_2 = 1$, we have

$$x = \mu - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{A}{10}, \quad (21)$$

$$y = \pm \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left(1 + \frac{A}{15} \right). \quad (22)$$

Hence the co-ordinates of the non-collinear libration points are (x, y) , where x and y are given in the Equations (21) and (22). If we put $A = 0$ in Equations (21) and (22), the obtained results are in conformity with Szebehely (1967).

6. Stability of the Libration Points

The equations of the motion of the infinitesimal mass are

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} &= \Omega_x \\ \ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} &= \Omega_y \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

To study the possible motion of the infinitesimal mass around the libration points let the coordinates of these points are (x_0, y_0) . If we give small displacement (α, β) to (x_0, y_0) , the variation α and β can be written as: $\alpha = x - x_0$ and $\beta = y - y_0$ and the equations of the motion become

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\alpha} - 2n\dot{\beta} &= \Omega_x(x_0 + \alpha, y_0 + \beta) = \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy}, \\ \ddot{\beta} + 2n\dot{\alpha} &= \Omega_y(x_0 + \alpha, y_0 + \beta) = \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where ‘o’ indicates that the partial derivatives are to be calculated at the libration points under consideration.

The characteristic equation of the Equations (24) is given by

$$\lambda^4 + (4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}) \lambda^2 + \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = 0, \quad (25)$$

which is a fourth degree equation in λ .

The libration point (x_0, y_0) is said to be stable if all the four roots of the Equation (25) are either negative real numbers or pure imaginary.

Let $\lambda^2 = \Lambda$, therefore the characteristic Equation (25) becomes

$$\Lambda^2 + (4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}) \Lambda + \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = 0 \quad (26)$$

which is a quadratic equation in Λ . If Λ_1 and Λ_2 are the roots of the Equation (26) then the roots of the characteristic Equation (25) are given by

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_1} \text{ and } \lambda_{3,4} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_2} \quad (27)$$

λ_i ($i=1,\dots,4$) will be pure imaginary if Λ_1 and Λ_2 both are negative real numbers and then the non-collinear libration points will be stable.

The values of Ω_{xx} , Ω_{yy} and Ω_{xy} at the non-collinear libration points are:

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} &= \frac{3}{4} - \frac{3}{5} \left(\mu + \frac{1}{8} \right) A, \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} &= \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2} \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{20} \left(13\mu - \frac{7}{2} \right) A, \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} &= \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{3}{2} - \mu \right) + \left(\frac{\mu}{4} - \frac{33}{40} \right) A. \end{aligned}$$

The roots of the Equation (26) are given by

$$\Lambda_{1,2} = \frac{-p_1 \pm \sqrt{p_1^2 - 4p_2}}{2}, \quad (28)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &= 4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} = \left(1 + \frac{3\mu}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{10} \left(1 - \frac{7\mu}{2} \right) A, \\ p_2 &= \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = \left(\frac{45\mu}{8} - \frac{27\mu^2}{4} \right) - \left(\frac{111\mu}{20} - \frac{27\mu^2}{4} \right) A. \end{aligned}$$

$\Lambda_{1,2}$ will be pure negative if $p_1^2 - 4p_2 = 0$ i.e.

$$\mu = \frac{-195 + 220A + \sqrt{26325 - 68400A}}{3(-195 + 173A)} < \frac{1}{2} \quad \forall A \text{ as shown in the Fig. 2.}$$

Fig. 2: A versus μ

From the Fig. 2, this is observed that there is negligible change in μ as A varies from 0 to 10^{-5} .

Also, $\Lambda_{1,2}$ exist if $p_1^2 - 4p_2 > 0$, therefore on plotting the graph of $p_1^2 - 4p_2$ with respect to mass parameter μ , considering $A = 10^{-5}$, we observed that $p_1^2 - 4p_2 > 0$ if $\mu < 0.0559836$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: $p_1^2 - 4p_2$ versus μ , $A = 10^{-3}$

Fig. 4: Λ_i ($i = 1, 2$) versus μ

Thus, $\Lambda_{1,2}$ are negative if $\mu < 0.0559836$ (Fig. 4). Hence the non-collinear libration points are stable for a critical value of mass parameter $\mu = \mu_c \leq 0.0559836$.

Conclusion:

W. D. MacMillan gave the potential of a homogeneous prolate spheroid in terms of largest root of the confocal spheroid in the book *The Theory of the Potential*, 1968. I have used this potential in restricted three-body problem to generalize the location of non-collinear libration points. Obviously, the oblateness factor A effects the location of the libration points as shown in the Eqns. (21) and (22). Since $A \ll 1$, therefore it does not effect very much on the critical value of mass parameter (Fig. 2). Finally, it is shown in the Fig. 4 that the non-collinear libration points are stable for a critical value of mass parameter $\mu = \mu_c \leq 0.0559836$.

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Idrisi, M. Javed / Existence and Stability of Non-Collinear Libration Points in Restricted Three-Body Problem When Smaller Primary is a Prolate Spheroid

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